

IMPLEMENTATION OF MERDEKA CURRICULUM IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF LEARNING IN MOVER SCHOOLS AT SMAN 18 KOTA BEKASI AND SMAN 10 GARUT

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Abstract

Kurikulum Merdeka Implementation in improving quality of learning in mover schools at SMAN 18 and SMAN 10 Garut follows the direction of policy and strategy of Kemdikbudristekdikti which emphasizes on the planning of Kurikulum Merdeka Implementation in improving learning quality of mover schools, including : planning of KOSP creation, schedule making, teaching module preparing, P5 module preparing, learning Media, Showing Material for general teaching and P5 modules, Organizing for obtaining the image of this research method is intended to analyze about: Execution, Evaluation, result, Solution and follow-up of Kurikulum Merdeka Implementation in improving quality of learning in mover schools at SMAN 18 Kota Bekasi and SMAN 10 Kabupaten Garut. The result of data extraction through interviews, observations and documentation study related to the solution of the result from Kurikulum Merdeka Implementation in improving quality of learning in mover schools program at SMAN 18 and SMAN 10 Garut shows that the program is already beginning to run, the teaching and learning process is already going, Intracurricular, extracurricular, and Co Project is also done well, plenty of learning, extraordinary learning experience experienced by involved parties, as well as extraordinary enthusiasm. It turns out being in line with goverment's hopes, that IKM (Implementasi Kurikulum Merdeka) is one of the priority programs across major units in the environment (Kemendikbudristek) which involves Badan Standar Kurikulum.

Keywords: Implementation of Kurikulum Merdeka, Quality of Learning, Mover School.

INTRODUCTION

National Education has a purposes and roles for building capabilities, shaping characters, as well as to advance the honorable national culture in order to improve intelligence of life of the society. The goals are to enrich individual potentials in learners so that they can become individuals with faith and obedience in The One and Only God, individuals with high morals, optimal health, broad knowledge, excellent skills, growing creativity, and capable of independence. Within the period of time that begins since the year of 1947 to the Curriculum of 2013, education in Indonesia has gone through changes of curriculum as many as eleven times. Although recurring changes of curriculum happened, basically the aim of this change is to make improvements and improvements to the previous curriculums. (Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan, 2021:49).

After being elected as Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology in Indonesia on October 23rd 2019, Nadiem Makarim introduces a number of innovative policies and programmes related to education in Indonesia. One of the leading program initiated by him is

Sekolah Penggerak (Afifah DE, 2023) or Mover School. The Program of Mover School is expected to be an entrance to the development of curriculum that is more suitable with the needs of learners as well as the characteristics of school environment in Indonesia (Unimma, 2022).

The Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology launches The Nover School Program in the academic year of 2021/2022. This program is still in the stage of gradual execution and requires structured assistance for schools that are selected as Mover Schools (Afifah DE, 2023).

The Ministry of Education and Culture initiated this program as a part of means of education reformation which goal is changing the culture of education. Nadiem stated that the strong points of Kurikulum Merdeka are it being more simple and more in-depth because it prioritizes essential materials and competence development of learners gradually. In this context, educators and learners will be more independent due to the absence of specialization in High School; learners are allowed to choose learning subjects according to their interest, talent, and aspiration.

With the introduction of Kurikulum Merdeka, the educators are faced with the complexity of 21st century challenges which demands more complex competence in responding to global education changes. Improving the quality of education in 21 era becomes the main focus, and education community has immense responsibility to overcome this challenge (Munawaroh, 2023). This requires acknowledgment that learners in 21 era have to possess the ability to hone competitive skills which emphasizes aspects such as the ability of critical thinking, problem solving, communication, mastering Teknologi Informasi dan Komunikasi (TIK) or Information and Communication Technology (ICT), information literacy, as well as media literacy (Rihadi, 2018).

Based on the research conducted by Rahayuningsih and partners (2022), Mover School Program consists of five intervention which each is related to one another and cannot be separated, including consultative assistance, strengthening of *sumber daya manusia* (SDM) or Human Resource (HR) at school, strengthening of principal role, school prefect role, as well as supervisor and educator. Learning with new paradigm emphasizes on strengthening competence and character building which is in line with Pancasila principles. This approach involves indoor and outdoor learning activity. In this context, students are not only given knowledge, but also given the chance to develop practical skills which are relevant with their future needs. On top of that, the values of Pancasila become the base of moral in every aspect of learning, building the character of student so that they become individuals with integrity, responsibility, and care towards one another and the environment. With this approach, it is expected for students to develop holistically, as well as to become competent and virtuous individuals, ready to face the challenges in globalization era (Hasnah, 2002).

In Kurikulum Merdeka, schools are given the freedom and independence to develop learning projects suitable with the characteristics of each education units. Project based learning is considered important for character building of learners since it is able to give them the chance

to learn through experience (experiential learning). With the implementation of Kurikulum Merdeka, few things are possible to be achieved: (1) Learners will be critical in thinking, responsive to problems, able to collaborate well, and responsible for their assignments. (2) Educator will teach according to the development and improvement of learners. (3) Interactive learning through project activities gives learners to actively support character and competence development in accordance with Profil Pelajar Pancasila.

The schools that are chosen to be the focus of this research are SMAN 18 Bekasi and SMAN 10 Garut, which are mover schools that implement Kurikulum Merdeka on early July of the 2023-2024 academic year. In conducting Kurikulum Merdeka, SMAN 18 Kota Bekasi and SMAN 10 Garut both arrange teaching plans customized to school needs, with utilizing curriculum frame prepared by Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology. The adjustment involves part of organization and learning planning so that it will be suitable with school context. The consideration of choosing these two schools is based on writer's observation which shows that both, based on previous research, are private schools that have achieved numbers of significant achievement.

Based on the matter above, writer was interested to do further research with research title about "Kurikulum Merdeka Implementation in improving quality of learning in mover schools at SMAN 18 Kota Bekasi and SMAN 10 Kabupaten Garut". Therefore, seeing from the background of research which was intriguing to be discussed, writer formulated research problems as follows:

Research Problems

1. How is the implementation of Kurikulum Merdeka improving the quality of learning at mover schools at SMAN 18 Bekasi and Garut?
2. How is the Evaluation of the Implementation of Kurikulum Merdeka in improving the quality of learning at mover schools at SMAN 18 Bekasi and Garut?
3. What are the results of the implementation of Kurikulum Merdeka in improving the quality of driving school learning at SMAN 18 Bekasi and Garut?
4. What is the solution from implementing Kurikulum Merdeka in improving the quality of learning at driving schools at SMAN 18 Bekasi and Garut?

What is the follow-up to the implementation of Kurikulum Merdeka in improving the quality of learning at driving schools at SMAN 18 Bekasi and Garut?

Research Objectives

a. General Objective

The general objective of this research is to study about the Implementation of Kurikulum Merdeka in improving quality of learning in mover schools at SMAN 18 Kota Bekasi and SMAN 10 Kabupaten Garut.

b. Special Objective

Special objective of this research is to obtain the image of how this research is purposed to analyze about: Execution, Evaluation, Result, Solution, and Follow Up of Implementation of Kurikulum Merdeka in improving quality of learning in mover schools at SMAN 18 Kota Bekasi and SMAN 10 Kabupaten Garut.

RESEARCH METHOD

The method used for this research is the qualitative method. In gathering the data for this researched, writer used various data needed for obtaining suitable information. The required data includes primary and secondary data, which obtained through various data gathering techniques. The variety of data gathering method used includes interviews, observation, and documentation study (AA Arni Amir, 2017).

This research selectively decides data source with special purpose, where the writer chose representative and reliable data to describe the implementation of Kurikulum Merdeka in improving quality of learning in moving schools (Oluwatosin Victor, 2023).

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Theoretical Basis

a. Education Knowledge Theory

Origin of education knowledge or *paedagogiek* comes from the greek word "pedagogues" and Latin word "paedagogus", which refers to a young man with the responsibility to bring children to school as well as guide them good behavior and discipline. The term then used to call educators (*pedagog*) and developed to *pedagogi* (pedagogy) concept as educating knowledge, that is known as the term *paedagogiek* in the context of education knowledge (DA Puspitasari, 2023).

Ki Hajar Dewantara states that Education is the process that demands the development of children in life. Which means, knowledge is about directing natural potential in children so that they are able to achieve optimal safety and happines as a human and as a member of society (M Sup, 2023)

b. Constructivism Theory

Constructivism theory has become familiar in the education world. Before understanding further about this theory, it is important to understand the base od constructivism itself. Constructivism refers to the process of knowledge and comprehension development. In the context of education philosophy, constructivism is the effort to build modern and cultured life structure (Cahyo, 2013:33). From the explanation, it could be understood that constructivism is a theory with the purpose of building skills and comprehension in learning process. With its constructive nature, it is expected that students' active participation in learning will improve their intelligence level.

2. Conceptual Basis

a. Kurikulum Merdeka Implementation

1) Definition of Kurikulum Merdeka Implementation

a) Definition of Implementation

Schubert (in Nugraha, 2019) defined implementation as a process of execution or application. In other context, implementation can also be considered as manipulation system, which refers to series of activities, action, measure, and mechanism in a system.

b) Curriculum

(1) The Essence of Curriculum

According to Mulyasa (2009:8), curriculum refers to series of plans and settings that include purpose, basic competence, standard material, learning result, and method that is used as a guidance in learning activity execution in order to achieve education goal.

Etimologically, the term "kurikulum" comes from Latin word, "Curriculum", which originally referred to teaching materials. There is also a relation with the French word, "Courier", which means running. Etimologically, curriculum can be traced to Greek word, where "Curier" refers to runner and "Curere" refers to the distance that a runner has to go through.

(2) Curriculum Component

The main components of curriculum include: 1. Purpose, that explains what needs to be attained by the school. 2. Teaching material, which decides how to choose learning materials achieving the goal of the purpose. 3. Teaching and learning process, which regulates how materials are taught effectively to learners. 4. Evaluation or grading, which are used to evaluate the effectiveness and learning process that have been done (Maskur, 2019).

(3) Principles of Curriculum

Conceptually and philosophically, the shaping of a curriculum has to be arranged based on certain principles and directions, which include philosophical, sociological, organizational, and psychological principles. Philosophical principle functions as a guidance in deciding general objective of education. Meanwhile, sociological principle gives a basis to decide material that will be taught according to needs and development of society, culture, and advancement of knowledge and technology (Maskur, 2019).

(4) Component of Curriculum Planning

The planning of curriculum has to consider the needs of society, learners characteristics, and scope of knowledge according to desired knowledge levels. Learners with that profile have two choices, which are continuing to pursue higher education or directly participate in the professional world. Hence, in the management of curriculum planning, it is important to pay attention to the purpose and content factor (Suhanda, 2013).

c) Kurikulum Merdeka

1) Kurikulum Merdeka

In implementing this Kurikulum Paradigma Baru, Kemendikbudristekdikti gives support to schools by providing various facilities, such as Buku Pendidik, learning module, as well as various formative evaluation, and development of education unit to support learning execution. However, it is advised for educators of subjects to prepare modules that they will teach. (DA Puspitasari, 2023).

2) Tujuan Kurikulum Merdeka

Kurikulum Merdeka is intended to overcome the challenges faced in the previous education system. This curriculum is intended to advance the potential and skills of learners. The mission of this curriculum is to explore potentials and support interactive learning. The approach of interactive learning supports active participation of learners and produce learning projects which trigger their interest, as well as allowing them to develop skills that are relevant with their environment. (DA Puspitasari, 2023).

3) Kurikulum Merdeka Characteristics

Kurikulum Merdeka has been designed with more flexible curriculum approach, where the focus is on core module as well as the development of personality and skills of learners. One of the particular characteristics of this curriculum that supports recovery learning is the utilization of project based learning, which is intended to develop personal skill and personality that is in line with Profil Pelajar Pancasila (Afifah DE, 2023).

b. Profil Pelajar Pancasila

Profil Pelajar Pancasila reflects the image of Indonesian learners that are filled with lifetime learning concept. This profile emphasizes on character building, holistic competence, and behaviors that are in line with Pancasila principles. As a main guidance in education and teaching, Profil Pelajar Pancasila becomes a standard for educators in shaping the characters and skills of learners (DA Puspitasari, 2023).

To broaden the comprehension towards dimension, elements, and subelements of Profil Pelajar Pancasila in the context of Kurikulum Merdeka, Kepala Badan Standar Kurikulum dan Asesmen Pendidikan (2022) published Surat Keputusan Nomor 009/H/KR/2022 about Dimensi Projek Penguatan Profil Pelajar Pancasila (P5). The Dimensi (Dimension) includes: a) Dimensi Keimanan, Ketaqwaan kepada Tuhan Yang Maha Esa, dan Akhlak Mulia (Dimensions of Faith, Devotion to One and Only God, and Noble Morals); b) Dimensi Keanekaragaman Global (Dimensions of Global Diversity); c) Dimensi Gotong Royong (Mutual Cooperation Dimensions); d) Dimensi Kemandirian (Independence Dimension); e) Dimensi Berpikir Kritis (Critical Thinking Dimensions); f) Dimensi Kreativitas (Creativity Dimension) (Sudibya I Gusti Ngurah, 2022).

c. Quality of Learning

In the context of education, understanding about quality refers to the quality of education process and result. High quality "education process" involves various input factors, such as learning material (be it cognitive, affective aspect, as well as psychomotor), teaching method (customized to the ability of educators), school facility, administrative support, and also conducive learning atmosphere (Kemdikbudristekdikti, 2018). Factors that affect learning quality refer to elements and situations that affects learning quality or learning success in a context of education.

d. Program Sekolah Penggerak

Program Sekolah Penggerak (Mover School Program) stresses on learning result of learners in a comprehensive way, which includes competence in literacy and numeracy as well as character building. The first step is to strengthen excellent human resource, including principal and educators. Accelerating school transformation is done in every kinds of schools, public as well as private schools, with the purpose of driving developments 1-2 steps ahead. Program Sekolah Penggerak is designed to be conducted gradually and integrated with the ecosystem so that all schools in Indonesia could take part of this program. The main characteristic of Program Sekolah Penggerak includes collaboration between Ministry of Education and Culture with Local Government, where the commitments of Local Government becomes the key of success; the scope of program that embraces all school conditions, not only leading schools, both public and private schools; program integration with various aspect of ecosystem so that all schools in Indonesia could be mover schools.

Intervention in this program is conducted comprehensively, starting from the improvement of human resource capacity in school, the change of learning approach, data-based planning, the utilization of digital technology in school environment, to assistance that is provided by Local Government for three years of learning. After the assistance period ends, schools are expected to continue the transformation process independently. Programs that are part of Mover Schools include Pendampingan Konsultatif dan Asimetri (Consultative Assistance and Assymetry), Penguatan SDM Sekolah (Strengthening of School Human Resource), Pembelajaran dengan Paradigma Baru (Learning with New Paradigm), Perencanaan Berbasis Data (Data-based Planning), and Digitalisasi Sekolah (School Digitalization). (Sarlin Patilima, 2021)

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Research Result

Based on the result of data gathering through in-depth interview, it is found that there was a key informant which had been given prior access to give deep knowledge related to problem topic that was being researched. This in-depth interview technique is done with various parties, including Principal, Tim Pengembangan Keprofesian Berkelanjutan (PKP Team), Vice Principal, Educator Representative, three Facilitator related with Indeks Kepuasan Masyarakat or IKM (Community Satisfaction Index), Observer that was involved in the assistance of Program Sekolah Penggerak, as well as learners. (CL, KL, Ob, Dok, September 2023)

Documentation study in this research involved data gathering through various sources, including direct visit, communication with the school, educators, educational staff, as well as learners. Moreover, data was also obtained from official website, social media accounts, flyers, and form letter that were regularly updated by SMAN 18 Kota Bekasi and SMAN 10 Garut. The purpose of this data collection is to obtain detailed image about activities, program, performance or leadership of the principal, regular activity related to follow up plan, performance report, as well as facilities and infrastructure related to Kurikulum Merdeka implementation in improving quality of learning in the mentioned mover schools. The data was also utilized to determine the needs of human resource. (CL, KL, Ob, Dok, September 2023)

Generally, evaluation has a purpose of being a problem solver for obstacles or constrained that occurred, which are detected through observation process, so that the steps of processes based on input components that has been decided could produced decided output and obtained in a suitable amount, time, usage, and purpose (CL, KL, Ob, Dok, September 2023).

The implementation result of Kurikulum Merdeka in improving quality of learning in mover schools at SMAN 18 Bekasi and SMAN 10 Garut showed that the program has started and has been running well. The learning process, both intracurricular, extracurricular, as well as Co Project, have been running well. There were many extraordinary learning and experience felt by all involved parties, there was also a high enthusiasm. This result is in line with the government's expectation that Program Sekolah Penggerak is one of the priority programs across major units in the environment of Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology. (CL, KL, Ob, Dok, November 2023)

The obstacle in implementing Kurikulum Merdeka includes internal and external factors. Internal factors involve psychological, administrative, organization, and budget management obstacles. For instance, the obstacles that are more specific include the readiness of The Principal and Tim Pengembangan Keprofesian Berkelanjutan (PKP Team) in arranging Learning Target, Learning Target Planning, Learning Material, Modul Penguatan Profil Pelajar Pancasila (P5) or P5 Module, as well as schedule arrangement and teaching duration arrangement related with activities in the curriculum, extracurricular, and Co-Project. Besides that, the execution of the program has not been structured well and Kerangka Operasional Sekolah Penggerak (KOSP) needs improvement, and the strong collaboration between principal and PKP team is needed.

External obstacle factor include the lack of understanding of educators, especially the educators that teach tenth grade, as well as general lack of understanding about the execution of Kurikulum Merdeka implementation, and the lack of confidence in P5 module creation. The relation between internal obstacle factors and external ones are related with the lack of understanding about Indeks Kepuasan Masyarakat or IKM (Community Satisfaction Index), the arrangement of Tujuan Pembelajaran or TP (Learning Objective), Alur Tujuan Pembelajaran or ATP (Learning Objective Flow), as well as administration. (CL, KL, Ob, Dok, November 2023)

The improvement of quality of learning in Mover School Program at SMAN 18 Bekasi can be overcome as time goes by with the presence of cooperation and commitment from all involved parties in school. Schools continuously experience development from various aspect, so that they become dynamic in facing changes, especially in the context of education. Although curriculum changes can create challenges for educators, with good cooperatiom, those challenges could be overcome. Kurikulum Sekolah Penggerak is the newest curriculum that is implemented in around 2.500 schools.

Educators, as the spearhead in the execution of the whole learning process with using Kurikulum Merdeka, are demanded to understand the profile, component, and substance from the curriculum so they could operate it more effectively in learning and teaching process (CL, KL, Ob, Dok, November 2023).

2. Discussion

Based on the research findings and interpretation about the findings, the discussion of the research is presented as follows:

In the contextr of Kurikulum Merdeka execution in Program Sekolah Penggerak, the role of the principal is crucial. The principal is responsible in doing coordination and the incorporation of all school components to achieve commitment in coaching. The function of execution management (actuating) that is done by principal includes coordination, briefing, and leadership. Therefore, Principal has a significant role in making sure that all school components could carry out tasks according to respective roles.

The importance of coordination and briefing from The Principal is also highlighted as the effort to prevent overlapping in the execution of administrative tasks. With the presence of good coordination, it is hoped that there will be a synergy betern all school management components so that the execution of Kurikulum Merdeka could run well and efficient (CL, KL, Ob, Dok, September 2023).

In the aspect of evaluation from Kurikulum Merdeka implementation to improve the quality of learning at SMAN 18 Bekasi and SMAN 10 Garut, the planned evaluation program has been implemented. Schools reported improvement and achievement to Facilitator through sessions of G meet once in every three months, using the link that was already provided by the related Facilitator with the program that will be executed and the program that had been done. Reporting was done with the format of Laporan Kegiatan (LK) that was already provided by Badan Pengembangan Guru dan Pendidikan (BBGP) Kemdikbudristekdikti. Besides that, in every three months, a reflection of workshops that involve some schools were done, with the number of participants matching the number of the guides.

The result of Kurikulum Merdeka Implementation in Mover School Program at SMAN 18 and SMAN 10 Garut, has a positive effect, including: Learning Achievement, Active participation, Critical thinking skill, Creativity, Interaction quality, and communication between educator and learners.

According to the statement of Principal, PKP Team, and Educator, which are concluded by researcher, the factors that affect achievement in improving quality of learning are as follows: Internal factors refer to the factors that came from the inside of an individual. Factors that are included in the category of internal factor include intelligence, talent, interest, and motivation. On the other side, external factor refers to the factors that could affect learning achievement of an individual and came from the outside of learners, such as experiences, family conditions, surrounding environment, and so on (CL, KL, Ob, Dok, Sept 2023).

Follow up on the Kurikulum Merdeka Implementation in improving quality of learning in mover schools at SMAN 18 and SMAN 10 Garut expects educators and educational staff that are in the same Education unit understand that Kurikulum Merdeka Implementation changes in each Education unit. Educators as a spearhead in the execution of the whole process of learning using Kurikulum Merdeka are expected to understand profile, component, and substance from Kurikulum Merdeka since it simplify operationalization of learning and teaching process for". Lastly, educators can make teaching modules, and preparation of P5 module. (CL, KL, Ob, Dok, Okt-Nov 2023)

CONCLUSION

Based on the research result and the discussion, it could be concluded that the execution of Kurikulum Merdeka Implementation at SMAN 18 Kota Bekasi and SMAN 10 Kabupaten Garut have given significant contribution in improving the quality of learning in both mover schools. Through data extraction from interviews, observation, and documentation study, the efforts to implement Kurikulum Merdeka in improving quality of learning have been done through educational staff empowerment.

Program Sekolah Penggerak at SMAN 18 and SMAN 10 Garut have been started well, and the learning process in class as well as outside of class learning have also been running smoothly. Intracurricular, extracurricular, as well as Co Project have also been well-executed, which show that Kurikulum Merdeka implementation has given positive effect in improving quality of learning in both schools. Program Sekolah Penggerak di SMAN 18 dan SMAN 10 Garut have been attempted through series of programs, including the improvement of comprehension, skills, and attitude to support the program execution. The attempts include various activities such as In House Training (IHT) execution step 1, 2, dan 3, as well as invitation of presenters related to Indeks Kepuasan Masyarakat (IKM). Besides that, socialization to learners and parents related to Kurikulum Merdeka implementation had been done.

Follow up in Kurikulum Merdeka implementation at SMAN 18 and SMAN 10 Garut has a purpose for educators and educational staff to be able to understand well about the concept and execution of Kurikulum Merdeka. It is hoped that they feel that they have changed from the previous curriculum to curriculum merdeka, and actively participating in activities and programs of Program Sekolah Penggerak. This matter is expected to be the supporter of change in quality of learning, in the achievement of education report as well as the literacy and numeracy of learners.

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